

A Study on Thiomalate Complexes of Ni(II), Mn(II) and Tl(I)

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Thiomalic acid has been reported to form complexes with some metals^{1,2}. Not much attempt, however, has been made to investigate the double bond character of the M-S linkage. Nyholm and coworkers³ observed the greater stability of phosphine and arsine complexes compared to ammonia and explained it on the basis of the π interaction in M-P and M-As bonds. The possibility of π -bonding in the M-S bonds has also been indicated in the literature⁴. According to Pettit and coworkers⁵ sulphur is known to form weak M $\rightarrow$ L π bonds. In a previous communication from this laboratory the possibility of π interaction in Nickel thiolactate complex has been indicated⁶. The present study has been undertaken with the point of view of studying the effect of π interaction on chelate stability and also to correlate the tendency of thiomalic acid to form complexes with Ni(II), Mn(II) and Tl(I).

EXPERIMENTAL AND DISCUSSION

The stepwise formation constants were determined by Irving-Rossotti method⁷. The solutions containing perchloric acid; perchloric acid+thiomalic acid; and perchloric acid+thiomalic acid+metal solution, maintained at constant volume (50 ml) and constant ionic strength (0.2M) by the addition of neutral salt NaClO₄, were titrated against standard alkali. The titrations were performed at 35, 45 and 55°. The values of $\bar{n}_A$, $\bar{n}$ and p^L were calculated from the equations given in the original paper⁷.

The proton-ligand stability constants have been determined by the following relationship :

$$\log {}^pK_n^H = B + \log \bar{n}_A / (1 - \bar{n}_A)$$

For the calculation of ${}^pK_1^H$, the points were chosen in the region where $\bar{n}_A$ is $> 0 < 1$, for ${}^pK_2^H$ the region where $\bar{n}_A$ is $> 1 < 2$ and ${}^pK_3^H$ was calculated from $\bar{n}_A > 2 < 3$. In the three different regions p^H was plotted against $\log \bar{n}_A / (1 - \bar{n}_A)$ and straight lines were obtained. The values of proton-ligand stability constants have been given in Table 1.

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TABLE 1

Thiomalic acid	PK_1^H	PK_2^H	PK_3^H	Temp. °C
	3.084×10^{10}	5.059×10^4	1.407×10^3	35
	1.291×10^{10}	3.995×10^4	1.108×10^3	45
	1.133×10^{10}	3.910×10^4	1.099×10^3	55

$\bar{n}$ and P^L were plotted to get the formation curves and $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were obtained from P^L at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. The values have been tabulated in Table 2. The values of formation constants have an accuracy of ± 0.05 .

TABLE 2

Complex	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	Temp. °C
Tl Thiomalate	3.90	—	35
	3.86	—	45
	3.82	—	55
Mn Thiomalate	4.92	—	35
	4.87	—	45
	4.82	—	55
Ni Thiomalate	7.54	6.39	35
	7.38	6.26	45
	7.22	6.12	55

The free energy change ΔF , the enthalpy change ΔH and the entropy change ΔS have been calculated with the help of temperature coefficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz equations. The plots of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ separately vs. $1/T$ resulted in straight lines indicating that the assumption in Gibbs-Helmholtz equation that ΔH is constant at different temperatures stands true. The ΔH and ΔS values involve errors ± 2 Kcals per mole and ± 7 cal per degree per mole respectively. The results have been tabulated in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Complex	$-\Delta F_1$ $-\Delta F_2$ K cals.		$-\Delta H_1$ $-\Delta H_2$ K cals.				$+\Delta S_1$ $+\Delta S_2$ cals.			
	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
Ni Thiomalate	10.63	9.01	7	7	6	6	11	11	10	10
Mn Thiomalate	6.94	—	2	2	—	—	16	16	—	—
Tl Thiomalate	5.49	—	2	2	—	—	11	11	—	—

A = ΔH and ΔS at 35° considering a temperature difference of 10° .

B = ΔH and ΔS at 35° considering a temperature difference of 20° .

From the experimental data it is clear that thallos thiomalate is less stable than manganese and nickel chelates. This can be attributed to the fact that thallos ion is a non-transition metal ion and also that the ionic potential of Tl(I) is low. However Mn(II) though having the same charge and smaller size than Ni(II) its thiomalate is not so stable as nickel thiomalate. The greater stability of the nickel thiomalate complex can be explained in terms of $M \rightarrow L \pi$ bonding. Due to the available vacant $d\pi$ orbitals on the sulphur atom there can be an interaction between it and the $d\pi$ orbitals of the nickel leading to synergic stabilization of $L \rightarrow M \sigma$ bond. The lower stability of Manganese thiomalate is probably because the π interaction is not enough to bring to the required splitting to overcome the high pairing energy in the half filled d shell of Mn(II). Tl(I) being a non-transition element has no available d electrons and hence no π interaction is possible. The higher $\log K_1/\log K_2$ value in Nickel thiomalate also indicate the possibility of π bond formation⁸.

Since ΔH and ΔS values involve errors a rigorous quantitative interpretation cannot be tried. However, a qualitative comparative discussion of the thermodynamic functions is worthwhile. The enthalpy changes in the reactions of a ligand with the metal ions having different number of d electrons are $d^5 < d^8 > d^{10}$.⁹ The ΔH values of Ni(II), Mn(II) and Tl(I) chelates with thiomalic acid obey the above order. The higher ΔH value in the case of nickel thiomalate also indicates the possibility of double bond between Ni-S and thus supports the $M \rightarrow S \pi$ interaction.

Since the thiomalic acid is a bidentate ligand and there is charge neutralisation during the formation of the chelate, the freedom gained by the solvent molecules is more, resulting in positive entropy change.

Authors' thanks are due to Prof. S. M. Sethna, Head, Department of Chemistry for providing all the laboratory facilities. Authors' thanks are also due to Council of Scientific and Industrial Research for the award of fellowship to one of the authors (M.V.R.).

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Received September 24, 1968.
Revised MSS received May 27, 1969.

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